

THE THEORY OF BILLINGUALISM IN THE ASPECT OF NEUROLINGUISTICS

Ergashova Munavvar Dilsiroj qizi

Navoiy Davlat Pedagogika Instituti

Ingliz tili va adabiyoti mutaxassisligi magistranti

ABSTRACT

This article deals with the basic theory of bilingualism in the aspect of neurolinguistics.

Keywords: bilingualism, neurology, bilingual, multilingual, anatomical, neurolinguistics.

It is generally argued that, bilingualism is the usage of two languages, either by an individual speaker or by a community of many speakers. Bilingualism is also the reference to the representation and effects of different kind of language systems in the whole brain. Bilingualism can strengthens cognitive thinking abilities in that case bilingual people tend to be much more flexible and they think logically and in a creative way. They can be more open –minded and they also find it easier to focus on a variety of tasks simultaneously. Moreover, being able to speak two or more languages helps in other fields of life as well.

Bilingualism-(multilingualism)refers to the coexistence of more than one language system within an individual, as contrasted to monolingualism. Difinition of bilingualism range from a minimal proficiency in two languages ,to an advanced level of proficiency ,which allows the speaker to function and appear as a native speaker of two languages.

A person may describe themselves as bilingual but may mean only the ability to converse and communicate orally. As for the neurolinguistics which is the branch of linguistics dealing with the relationship between language and the structure and

function of the brain. Moreover, it is defined as the relationship between language and communication, to to different aspects of brain function meaning that, how our brain understands and and produce language. Neurolinguistics is the study of the biological and neural foundation of language. The research is often based on data from a typical or impaired language and uses such data to understand properties of human language in general. In some cases neurolinguistics is believed that it is the study of neural mechanism in the human brain that control the comprehension, production and acquisition of language. Also there are several scientists who research about the main theory and the function of neurolinguistics in the aspect of bilingualism. One of them is Harry Whitaker, who founded the journal of neurolinnguistics in 1985.

It is generally argued that, neurolinguistics is a new area of interest of psycholinguistics; neurological bases of human language functioning with language and brain. It also studies that where do language formulation and understanding reside in the brain and it discovers what anatomical structures underline normal development and use of full range of skills. There are also a great number of hot debates in the idea of three broad phases of cognitive (neurolinguistic) research on the relation of language and the brain are discerned. The modern cognitive neurolinguistics is the main base of the language and it also helps brain formulate the speech and understanding the language peculiarities. It si meant that our brains store information in networks of brain cells. These neural networks are ultimately connected to the parts of the brain that control our movements (including those are the main to produce our speech) and our internal and external sensation such as our sounds, sights, touches, and those are appeared with the help of our brain and movement. The connections within these networks may be strong or weak and the information that our brain sends out may increase the activity of others.

Neurolinguistics is also important because it studies the mechanisms and the main features of human brain and that control hearing, seeing, comprehending, and speaking of the language.

As for the history of neurolinguistics, historically this term has been most closely connected with aphasiology, the study of linguistic deficits, and spared abilities, occurring as a result of brain damage. Although aphasiology is the historical core of neurolinguistics, in recent years the field has broadened considerably, as new technologies have emerged. Language is a fundamental topic of interest in cognitive neuroscience, and modern brain imaging techniques have contributed greatly to a growing understanding of the anatomical organization of linguistic functions. Such techniques include brain and its different type of functions which provide high spatial resolution images of energy utilized in various brain regions during language processing tasks. To date, the results of these techniques have not contradicted the existing results from aphasiology. Unfortunately, the techniques do not allow for high temporal resolution of brain activity as the comprehension or production of sentences unfold. At the present time there are some new developments in the study of brain functions. Among newer noninvasive techniques to study the workings of the brain, including how language works, transcranial magnetic stimulation is also worthy of mention. Neurolinguistics is the basic human need that helps the human being to improve their whole life and all field of their academic success. Neurolinguistic programming is an interpersonal communication system, developed by John Grinder an associate professor of linguistics and Richard Bandler, a mathematician and a graduate student of psychology, in the early 1970 as a new method to language teaching. It is a collection of strategies, techniques, and patterns which are used for effective communication, growth and personal change.

REFERENCES:

1. Alamdar , F.S &Karbalaeei, A (2015).The relationship between Neurolinguistic programming and anxiety and self esteem among Iranian intermediate EFL learners .

2. Rustan , E (2017). Learning Creative Writing Model Based on Neurolinguistic Programming . International Journal of Language education and Culture Review 3(2) 13-29.

3. Tremblay ,A . Proficiency assessment standarts in second language acquisition research : “Clozing the gap “. Studies in Second Language Acquisition , 33,339-372.

4. Grosjean , F(1998).Transfer and language mode .Bilingualism :Language and Cognition,1,175-176.

